

**SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ADVOCATION - A FACTOR OF
ELIMINATING IDEOLOGICAL THREATS****M. T. Vakhabov****Senior teacher of the Department of Social and Humanities, Physical Culture and
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Key words. Globalization, economic globalization, ideology, spiritual life, propaganda and propaganda, ideological threat, ideological polygon, struggle for human mind and soul, ideological landscape of the world, ideological weapon, world community, stability and instability, idea, value, transnational corporation , anti-globalization, tendency.

Annotation. In this article, the main trends of spiritual life and ideological processes in the current globalization period, the changes (correctives) that are introducing the phenomenon of propaganda and propaganda, the spiritual and ideological threats that are becoming more and more dangerous, and subjective factors such as propaganda and propaganda in the fight against them. its significance is analyzed philosophically.

Also, today, when the struggle for the human mind and soul is stronger than ever, and "ideological landfills are more powerful than nuclear landfills"¹, the methods and means of organizing propaganda and agitation, which are considered the main means of preserving and improving spirituality, are scientifically based.

The main part. The negative consequences of globalization processes in the world, the widening scope of new ideological dangers and threats increase the importance of this issue. In this process, it is required to give special importance to the following.

In the works of Uzbek philosophers, such as S.Otamurotov², Sh.Kahhorova³, A.Ochildiev⁴, U.Saidov⁵, and others, a number of aspects of the globalization process, particularly its ideological foundations, influence on the ideological landscape of the world, national development, and intercultural communication have been analyzed. Especially in the works of the late Abduvahid Ochildiev, doctor of philosophy, there are important developments on our topic. At the same time, the attention paid to psychological warfare, the reactionary activity of geostrategic centers, which are actively promoting norms and concepts alien to humanity on a global scale, have not been critically analyzed or exposed. spread out.

In everyday life, it is common to understand globalization as a problem of universal importance. Such an understanding is one-sided and fails to reveal its essence and leads to the interpretation of globalization only as a negative phenomenon. In a broad sense, globalization means that a certain idea, value (or evil), process has gone beyond the national borders and covered the globe, entering the life of many other countries and peoples.

In the 20th year of the 21st century, the spread of the "Coronavirus" pandemic around the world, that is, its global scale, also became the basis for a number of philosophical conclusions; in particular, this global disaster indicates that the globe has "shrunk", the world's population has become a "whole organism", and territorial borders are disappearing. In the Middle Ages, for example, the people of other continents did not know about the plague, which killed a third of the population of Europe. It is also known that the news of the start of the First World War reached the village of Abdulla Qahhor⁷ in 4 months. Now the situation has completely changed, and the main vector of these changes is globalization processes.

Therefore, the process of globalization, which appeared in the framework of international trade, that is, the occupation of the world market in a very short period of time, first spread to the economic sphere, and transnational corporations, which do not know national borders, developed. At the next stage, globalization began to cover the spheres of social, political, and spiritual life. On the one hand, the supporters of the globalization process and the categories and groups that benefited from it appeared, and on the other side, the supporters of restraining and stopping this process, if possible, gathered, and a movement against it - the anti-globalization movement - was formed.

It is a philosophical fact that when a new phenomenon appears in life, both its supporters and its opponents appear. Because any event or process is not absolutely good or absolutely bad, it has both positive and negative aspects. Globalization is no exception.

Many scientific opinions and philosophical conclusions about the process of globalization, its positive and negative aspects, and its impact on spiritual life are presented. It is emphasized that this complex and conflicting process is rapidly entering our lives, and it is impossible to stay away from it.

There is enough information in the literature about the positive aspects of the globalization process.

One of the negative aspects of globalization is that it undermines the uniqueness of the life, lifestyle and culture of different peoples, the realization of national identity, it sows the seeds of immorality on the ground where a spiritual void has arisen, and it becomes a sharp and

dangerous weapon of ideological influence. Since the struggle for the human mind and soul is being waged on a global scale, propaganda and propaganda are also becoming global in nature.

In recent years, two trends have emerged as a specific reflection of the globalization process: firstly, national-cultural awakening and, secondly, cultural integration, mutual convergence and enrichment of national cultures, and the decline of cultural identity. It is not easy to give a clear answer to the questions of which of these will take priority, and if so, when it will happen. But one thing is certain: the dominant character of one of these trends in the long perspective of the development of human culture would have been a sign of the impoverishment of humanity and its culture.

Therefore, in order to avoid this, it is possible to hope that humanity will discover new ways to ensure the dialectic unity of these two trends, and that each national culture will be able to preserve its identity while forming aspects that are common and similar to other cultures.

Witnessing the unique cultures that have perished due to various reasons, many political systems that have attacked humanity, and the world wars that have brought human civilization to the brink of destruction, the deeper understanding of the identity and integrity of humanity proves that such a hope has its own solid foundation.

Preservation of the national culture and spirituality of different peoples, which is happening on a large scale throughout the world and has been formed for centuries, from the negative and destructive effects of globalization, is the most important issue facing every nation. Taking this into account, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev launched a new campaign of Uzbekistan's development under the slogan "From national revival to national rise". This strategic goal, this great conceptual idea, this deep philosophical wisdom, covering and scientifically based speeches and articles were published as a collection⁹.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted the following: "Today, Uzbekistan is entering a new, high stage of its development. We have made it our most important and priority task to achieve national revival - national rise. We are well aware that this great goal can be achieved only by living in harmony and cooperation with the people of the world, building an open democratic society, and establishing a greater sense of respect for national and universal values in our lives"¹⁰.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev specifically stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, we must develop such a national idea that such a constructive idea will lead us to the high goals ahead of us. On April 8, 2019, the President signed the decree "On measures to develop the concept of the development of the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development",

and on May 3, he signed the Resolution "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work"¹¹. The need for the adoption of these documents is that the national idea harmonizes the goals of the state with the goals of the people. Forming the belief of "one region - one nation", it unites the people of the countries and mobilizes them towards a common goal.

In these documents, it was mentioned that it is necessary to further improve propaganda and propaganda work, to introduce methods and forms that meet the requirements of the time. Propaganda and agitation, as a global phenomenon, should have their own characteristics and new qualities, because globalization is a very large-scale process, and its manifestation in various fields has its own characteristics.

There is no doubt that the implementation of globalization in the economic sphere has become the central and main problem of international life, and countries can solve it only through mutual cooperation. Globalization in the economy is the basis of globalization in all areas.

This can be seen in the fact that most of the countries of the world produce products for export, 25% of the global product is exported. This shows that all countries are involved in international economic relations. But it should not be forgotten that the level of involvement of different countries in such relations is qualitatively different from each other.

The President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has been paying special attention to expanding the export volume and increasing the assortment. These issues were discussed in detail at the video selector meeting held on January 15, 2020. Thanks to the implemented efforts, the country's export capacity increased by 28% in 1 year, including the regional industrial export that increased 2 times¹².

Economic globalization is an inherently objective process. This process ensures that science and technology, new technologies and innovations enter all spheres of society's life, wide diversification of production, and increase in the quality of goods.

At the same time, it creates a number of problems for relatively underdeveloped countries, in particular, the disproportionate distribution of the benefits of globalization. In particular, according to the information of the environmental organization Worldwatch Institute, 12% of the population of the Earth living in Europe and North America consumes 60% of the benefits created in the world¹³.

It should be noted that economic globalization is the cause of increasing anti-globalization movements because it creates a disproportionate distribution of wealth and benefits.

In the following words of Mahatma Gandhi, the aspects of globalization, especially economic globalization, are very beautifully expressed: "I cannot keep the gates and doors of my house tightly closed. Because it needs fresh air. And at the same time, I don't want the air coming in through my doors and windows to become a hurricane, overturning my house and knocking me down"¹⁴.

At this point, it is worth mentioning about the "Global Government", which is being created in the desire to rule the whole world. It is known that the extremely complex and conflicting processes taking place in the world, sometimes unexpectedly, cause various shifts, due to which the relations between the various driving forces entering into communication with each other are taking a specific direction. That is, each geopolitical power is seeking its own interests and trying to realize them in any way possible. All this gives instability to international life, on the one hand. On the other hand, these same processes require that there should be a system of political administration with a certain structure and order on a global scale.

Realizing this necessity, some experts and political figures suggest that a separate body - "Global Governance" - i.e. "Global Policy" or "Global Government" should be created to manage world politics.

In our opinion, it is neither possible nor necessary to create such a government that is above individual states and nations. Because there is an authoritative organization like the United Nations, which has sufficient authority to regulate international relations and implement world politics. The main idea is to increase the responsibility of the subjects of world politics, to strengthen the involvement of each state and political power in the work of maintaining peace around the world.

Disrespect for international relations, indifference and indifference to the norms of international law cause great harm to humanity.

Already, humanity had the "opportunity" to clearly observe such a situation in the practice of the international community and international politics, which caused a lot of damage in terms of the stability and security of each subject, in the practice of dividing the world into mutually hostile parties without thinking about its future.

Today, the bitter experience of those fruitless arguments and bloody conflicts has not gone in vain. Humanity, all political-intellectual circles, various international and regional institutions have come to approach international life and politics from a completely different point of view. It is now widely recognized that playing with international life is a great detriment to stability and common human interest.

Of course, the universal desire to fundamentally change the approach to it, the recognition by the relevant political and intellectual circles of the extreme complexity of international life as a system, did not happen today or yesterday.

It became clear that the deepening of the process of contradiction, complexity, a rational approach to it, otherwise not noticing it, will lead to many unpleasant consequences. In fact, international life, no matter how natural interstate relations are, still, due to the interference of people and relevant responsible organizations and groups, there is a constant need for educational guidance.

Changing views on international life based on the interests of the peoples of the world has been a concern of mankind for a long time. International organizations should primarily serve such interests.

They should maintain peace on Earth, ensure free and prosperous life, encourage mutual solidarity and cooperation. In the recent past, many wars and conflicts have arisen due to the stupidity of international organizations with a military-political spirit. In the current conditions, the role and reputation of international organizations that prioritize the interests of the world community is very high.

The world community is a concept that means the unity of the existing countries in the world in solving the global problems facing humanity in cooperation, working towards a common goal. The world community is based on the international legal principle that expresses the sovereign equality of all states. The world community is not considered an independent association or organization in international law. The United Nations is a universal organization that represents the world community.

Uzbekistan has been an equal member of the UN since March 2, 1992.

During the study of the essence and content of international life, the place and role of international organizations, a number of approaches, principles, and various methods have been formed in the science of political science. The system of views that has been formed or is being formed is diverse and each of them deserves special attention. International life is a system of various relations between regions, states and groups, which are obliged to enter into mutual communication. Regardless of the will, interests and goals of such regions, countries, groups and individuals, they are drawn into the system of international relations¹⁶.

If a war or bloodshed occurs in neighboring countries, or in the region, in any part of the Earth in general, it creates panic in the hearts of people in other places, increases anxiety and danger.

The above-mentioned objective and subjective tendencies, conscious and unconscious influences and reactions, on the one hand, form a unique immunity in the system on a global scale and ensure its survival. On the other hand, the failure of some states to take into account universal interests and to pursue their own geopolitical goals clearly shows that the international relations system is unstable.

We said that there are reasons for both stability and instability in the international arena. It is clear to everyone that all conflicts in the system of international relations cannot be solved in one day and easily. But there are many factors and reasons that bring different states and countries, nations and peoples closer together. It is a matter of maintaining the balance of both processes - stability and instability, that is, achieving their balance, restraining each other and creating conditions for their positive trends. This can be achieved by raising the level of enlightenment of the international system, by increasing the role of spiritual and moral factors. Therefore, the time demands that the development of world politics, international relations, and international organizations should be conducted on the basis of a systematic approach, mutual agreement (consensus), and the principles of humanization. Because there are still very complicated and painful points on Earth, problems and hardships that cannot be solved while there is an opportunity to solve them.

In the system of issues that concern humanity, social problems are distinguished by their severity and scale. In particular, the data presented in the UN Millennium Report¹⁷ show that 46.3% of the world's population lives in great difficulties. More than 1 billion people lack access to clean drinking water. About 840 million people are malnourished. Every 7 seconds, 1 child dies of hunger or malnutrition.

These numbers indicate, on the one hand, that the process of sharp polarization, which can be called wealth and poverty, is deepening in the life of the individual society, and on the other hand, there is a ground for social crises.

"The history of civilization can be summed up in six words: the more you know, the more you can do," wrote the French writer Edmont Abou. From these words, it is not difficult to understand that knowledge is a force that glorifies a person and leads him to perfection. From this point of view, it is sad that approximately 1 billion people have no access to any education at all, when we look at the present day, when humanity has made incredible progress in its development. This number shows that solving social problems has literally become a matter of human destiny.

It shows that humanity has the power, potential and ability to solve the social problems it faces. For this, it is necessary for humanity to realize its unity and wholeness, that the existing problems and their solution are relevant to its destiny.

Summary. Propaganda and propaganda is a social phenomenon as old as humanity itself, large-scale and multidimensional, and it is manifested in almost all aspects of society and human life. Of the three factors that shape personality - heredity, upbringing and social environment, the last two are directly related to propaganda. In essence, the educational process is carried out by instilling certain knowledge into the mind of the student, that is, by promoting it. Although the form and means of this event, which is represented by the terms of propaganda and agitation in the West, have changed, but its essence has remained the same and its importance has not disappeared. Changes in the world geopolitical space and information space, the rapid development of the Internet and mass media, and the penetration of modern technologies into the field of propaganda and propaganda have raised this field to a high level. It is no exaggeration to say that it is not an exaggeration to say that it is time to replace the phrase "whoever has information - rules the world" in the recent past with the thesis "whoever has strong propaganda - he will rule the world". Advertising, which has become the most global form of propaganda, has covered the whole world like a spider's web.

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